

PRISMA PROCESS – Global insights in giftedness research: mapping current characteristics and challenges

Table 1.
Research categories and questions

Category Dimension	Question	Type of answer sought
Publication metrics	RQ1: How many studies are found in the Scopus and WoS databases in the period from 2012 to 2024?	Number of articles for each database
	RQ2: In which countries have projects taken place?	Countries where research has been conducted
	RQ3: What are the affiliation countries of the studies' lead authors?	Name of countries
	RQ4: Which journals publish the most articles on the topic?	Journal names
	RQ5: What are the most common keywords used by authors?	Keyword cloud
Study Methodology	RQ6: What research designs are utilised in the studies?	Empirical research Systematic review Methodological study Case study
	RQ7: What types of research approaches are used in the articles?	Qualitative Quantitative Mixed
	RQ8: Which data gathering techniques are utilised in the studies?	Questionnaire Survey Interview
Giftedness Identification and Support	RQ9: What primary characteristics of giftedness are identified in the studies?	Characteristics
	RQ10: Who diagnoses giftedness in the studies?	Teachers Specialist Parents Self-assessment
	RQ11: What school levels are targeted by the studies/interventions?	Preschool Elementary Secondary High School Bachelor Other
	RQ12: What support facilities are provided for gifted individuals in the studies?	Special classes Normal School Special school

		Extra courses
	RQ13: What tools/methods are used to diagnose or identify giftedness in the studies?	Scale Psychometrics Interview Assessment Observation
Technology used	RQ14: What digital technologies are used in the studies/research?	Name of the digital technology
	RQ15: If utilised, what are the reasons for using digital technologies in the studies/research?	Reasons

Table 2.
Search chains used in indexing systems.

Scopus	WoS
TITLE-ABS-KEY (gifted AND characteristics) AND PUBYEAR > 2012 AND PUBYEAR < 2024 AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE, "j"))	TITLE-ABS-KEY (gifted AND characteristics) AND (LIMIT-TO (OA , "all")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2012)) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "j"))

Figure 1.
PRISMA workflow for a Systematic Literature Review.

RESULTS

PRISMA analysis, with its respective inclusion and exclusion criteria, led to the selection of 37 studies. To answer the research questions, the database was analyzed according to the categories of publication metrics, study methodology, giftedness identification and support, and technology used.

3.1 Publication metrics

RQ1. *How many studies are found in the Scopus and WoS databases in the period from 2012 to 2024?*

Among the total number of studies found, 376 were from Scopus and 300 from WoS. Furthermore, of the 37 studies selected, 22 were conducted between 2020 and 2022.

RQ2. *In which countries have projects taken place?*

RQ3. *What are the affiliation countries of the studies' lead authors?* No difference was found in the articles published in terms of the place where the study was conducted and the author's affiliation; therefore, the results of both questions were the same: Turkey with nine articles and Saudi Arabia with four.

Figure 2.

Countries involved in giftedness publication.

RQ4. Which journals publish the most articles on the topic?

We found that the journals with the highest number of publications were the Journal for the Education of Gifted Young Scientists (5), Frontiers in Psychology (3), Gifted Education International (2), International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change (2), Journal of Advanced Academics (2), and Pegem Egitim ve Ogretim Dergisi (2). The nations of origin of these journals are Turkey (2), the USA (2), Switzerland (1), and the UK (1).

RQ5. What are the most common keywords used by authors?

The most used keywords and the number of articles included were: gifted (38), characteristics (18), giftedness (16), students (14) and children (10).

Figure 3.

Keywords most used by authors.

RQ10. *Who diagnoses giftedness in the studies?*

According to the findings of this study, these students' diagnoses are usually made mainly by teachers or specialists in the subject. Teachers, with 17 mentions and specialists, had 10 mentions. Given their closeness to students, parents may also participate in the diagnostic process, as mentioned in two articles. Finally, self-evaluation was mentioned on two occasions.

RQ11. *What school levels are targeted by the studies/interventions?*

The studies/interventions were mainly focused on the primary and preschool levels, with a total of 16 and six respectively. This reflects a significant focus on early childhood and the first years of formal education. However, only five studies have been conducted on higher education. In addition, six studies were found to focus on secondary education. This variety in educational levels addressed in the studies provides a broad perspective on interventions and their effects at different stages of academic development.

RQ12. *What support facilities are provided for gifted individuals in the studies?*

Of the 37 studies, 21 did not specify the infrastructure offered to students. On the other hand, those that mention a special infrastructure are normal school (8), special school (4), special shift (2), extra courses (2) and science and art courses/pull out education (1).

RQ13. *What tools/methods are used to diagnose or identify giftedness in the studies?* As shown in Figure 4, the main tools used to identify them are psychometrics (14) and observation (8) without specifying a method. Among the psychometrics mentioned in some studies are the following: attention measurement (ANT), lexicometry analysis of the content of interviews with teachers, Creative Problem-Solving Features Inventory, Scale for Rating the Behavioural Characteristics of Gifted and Talented Students, and Social Skills Rating System and Socio-demographic Questionnaire.

Figure 4.

Tools for identifying gifted students

3.4 Technology used in research projects

RQ14. *What digital technologies are used in the studies/research?*

The technology used was displayed in only 17 of the studies. The software used in the articles was: Psychopy, Microsoft Teams, Google Forms, Alceste, SPSS Statistics 26, Office 365 (Excel), Nvivo 10.0, PERMATApintar National Gifted Center, SAM, Novo and Nearest neighbor.

RQ15. *If utilised, what are the reasons for using digital technologies in the studies/research?*

As shown in Figure 5, the reasons for using the technology were data analysis (52.94%), communication with participants (29.41%), and psychometry evaluation (17.65%).

Figure 5.

Reasons for using technology.

